

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF *p,p'*-BIS(SUBSTITUTED-BENZOYLAMINO-1,3,4-OXADIAZOL-5-YLMETHYL-AMINO)DIPHENYLSULPHONES*

R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
Phenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₆ S	180	75
<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₆ S	145	73
<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₆ S	215	80
<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₆ S	232	73
2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₆ S	236	62
2,6-Dihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₆ S	272	54
3,5-Dihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₆ S	222	58
3,4,5-Trihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₀ O ₅ N ₆ S	253	66
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₆ SCl	186	77
<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₆ SCl	138	82
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₆ SCl	235	54
<i>o</i> -Aminophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₁₀ S	325	60
<i>m</i> -Aminophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₁₀ S	239	72
<i>p</i> -Aminophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₁₀ S	360	70
3-Pyridyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₁₀ S	212	82
4-Pyridyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₁₀ S	238	73
2-Hydroxy-3,5-dinitrophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₁₄ S	208	69
1-Hydroxy-2-naphthyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₆ S	190	73
2-Hydroxy-3-naphthyl	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₆ S	183	82
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₁₀ S	176	65
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₁₀ S	212	80
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₁₀ S	192	72
3,5-Dinitrophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₁₄ S	238	68
<i>o</i> -Acetyloxyphenyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₆ S	218	60
Cinnamyl	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₆ S	158	64
β -Phenethylcinnamyl	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₆ S	360	81
<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₆ SBr	208	79
Benzyl	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₆ S	228	68
Benzylaminomethyl	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₂ N ₁₀ S	176	70

*Satisfactory elemental analyses were obtained.

out at a concentration of 100 μ g using gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. citreus*) and gram-negative (*Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhosa*) bacteria. The antifungal testing was carried out against *Aspergillus niger*, *Neurospora cressa*. The antimicrobial activity of the compounds was compared with chloromycetin, penicillin G, penicillin K and streptomycin at the same concentration level. It was observed that most of the compounds showed moderate activity against different strains of bacteria and fungi.

Maximum activity was observed in case of compounds having R = *m*-chlorophenyl, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-hydroxyphenyl and benzylaminomethyl against *S. citreus* and good activity against *A. niger* for compounds having R = 3-pyridyl, 4-pyridyl, 3,4,5-trihydroxyphenyl, 3,5-dihydroxyphenyl, *o*-acetyloxyphenyl and *p*-nitrophenyl.

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Studies on 4-Thiazolidinones. Part-VI. Synthesis and Antimicrobial activity of 2-Aryl-3-(2',4'-dibutylamino-*s*-triazin-6'-yl)-5-H/methyl/carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones

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4-Thiazolidinones are associated with various kinds of biological activities¹. *s*-Triazine derivatives also possess various biological activities². In order to synthesise more active drugs, we have prepared 4-thiazolidinone derivatives of type 1 by the action of thioglycolic acid, thiolactic acid and thiomalic acid on Schiff bases obtained by

1, R = Aryl, X = H/CH₃/OH, COOH

condensing 2,4-dibutylamino-6-amino-*s*-triazine with different aromatic aldehydes. The constitution of the product was supported by its spectral study. The products were screened for antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer.

2,4-Dibutylamino-6-amino-*s*-triazine: 2,4-Dibutylamino-6-chloro-*s*-triazine³ (0.01 mol) in dioxane was treated with ammonia (0.01 mol) at 80–90° for 1.5 h. The product was isolated and crystallised, (80%), m.p. 203° (Found: C, 55.31; H, 8.99; N, 35.11. C₁₁H₂₂N₆ requires: C, 55.46; H, 9.24; N, 35.3%).

2,4-Dibutylamino-6-benzalamino-s-triazine : A mixture of 2,4-dibutylamino-6-amino-s-triazine (0.01 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 6 h at 70–80°. The product was isolated and crystallised, (70%), m.p. 208° (Found : C, 66.11 ; H, 7.63 ; N, 25.31. $C_{18}H_{26}N_6$ requires : C, 66.26 ; H, 7.78 ; N, 25.77%) ; ν_{max} (R=*m*-hydroxyphenyl) 3 250, 3 100, 2 950, 2 860, 1 640, 1 460, 795 and 750 cm^{-1} .

Similarly, other aldehydes were condensed (Table 1).

sodium bicarbonate and water. The product was isolated and crystallised, (60%), m.p. 190d (Found : C, 59.3 ; H, 6.89 ; N, 20.83. $C_{20}H_{28}ON_6S$ requires : C, 60 ; H, 7 ; N, 21%) ; ν_{max} (R=*m*-hydroxyphenyl) 3 275, 3 100, 2 950, 1 700, 1 630, 1 580, 1 430, 1 300, 1 140, 790 and 595 cm^{-1} .

Similarly, other Schiff bases were condensed (Table 1).

2-Phenyl-3-(2',4'-dibutylamino-s-triazin-6'-yl)-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone : Thiolactic acid (0.01 mol) was added to 2,4-dibutylamino-6-benzalamino-s-triazine (0.01 mol) in benzene (25 ml) and refluxed for 6 h. The contents were diluted with cold water. The upper organic layer was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and water. The product was isolated and crystallised, (59%), m.p. > 300° (Found : C, 60.79 ; H, 7.13 ; N, 19.99. $C_{21}H_{30}ON_6S$ requires : C, 60.86 ; H, 7.24 ; N, 20.3%) ; ν_{max} (R=*m*-hydroxyphenyl) 3 250, 3 010, 2 950, 1 700, 1 630, 1 580, 1 510, 1 300, 1 140, 790 and 595 cm^{-1} .

Similarly, other Schiff bases were condensed (Table 1).

2-Phenyl-3-(2',4'-dibutylamino-s-triazin-6'-yl)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone : 2,4-Dibutylamino-6-benzalamino-s-triazine (0.01 mol) was condensed with thiomalic acid (0.01 mol) in presence of zinc chloride (0.5 g) at 160° for 2 h. The temperature was then raised to 180° for 0.5 h. The product was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution and reprecipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid and crystallised, (60%), m.p. > 300° (Found : C, 57.58 ; H, 6.39 ; N, 18.19. $C_{22}H_{30}O_2N_6S$ requires : C, 57.64 ; H, 6.55 ; N, 18.34%) ; ν_{max} (R=*o*-chlorophenyl) 3 300–2 300, 1 690, 1 620, 1 580, 1 510, 1 390, 1 355, 1 310, 1 230, 790 and 610 cm^{-1} .

Similarly, other Schiff bases were condensed (Table 1).

Antimicrobial activity : All the compounds were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities using cup-plate⁴ method. The testing was carried out at a concentration of 50 μg , using gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and *S. citreus*, gram-negative bacteria *Marcans serratia* and *Escherichia coli*, and fungi *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Aspergillus niger*. Under identical conditions the standard antibiotics chloromycetin showed a zone of inhibition 30–35 mm, streptomycin 20–25 mm and penicillin 20–33 mm against the various strains of bacteria and fungi at 50 μg concentration. Most of the compounds showed moderate activity (14–17 mm) against different strains of bacteria and fungi.

The most active among the Schiff bases are bearing (alongwith the zone of inhibition in mm) R=phenyl (17–28), anisyl (17–20), *p*-hydroxyphenyl (17–19), *m*-hydroxyphenyl (18–22), cinnamyl (17–20), *p*-chlorophenyl (17–19) and *o*-chlorophenyl (17–19). The most active among 2-aryl-3-(2',4'-dibutylamino-s-triazin-6'-yl)-4-thiazolidinones are bearing (alongwith the zone of inhibition in mm), R=phenyl (18–22), *p*-hydroxyphenyl (19–

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Sl. no	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
2,4-Dibutyl-6-benzalamino-s-triazines				
1.	Phenyl	$C_{18}H_{26}N_6$	208	70
2.	Anisyl	$C_{19}H_{28}ON_6$	216	65
3.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	$C_{19}H_{26}ON_6$	205	73
4.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	$C_{19}H_{26}ON_6$	214	71
5.	Salicyl	$C_{19}H_{26}ON_6$	207	69
6.	Cinnamyl	$C_{20}H_{28}N_6$	219	73
7.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	$C_{20}H_{30}O_2N_6$	210	78
8.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	$C_{18}H_{25}N_6Cl$	170	80
9.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	$C_{18}H_{25}N_6Cl$	202	76
2-Aryl-3-(2',4'-dibutylamino-s-triazin-6'-yl)-4-thiazolidinones				
10.	Phenyl	$C_{20}H_{28}ON_6S$	190d	60
11.	Anisyl	$C_{21}H_{30}O_2N_6S$	300	53
12.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	$C_{20}H_{28}O_2N_6S$	200d	68
13.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	$C_{20}H_{28}O_2N_6S$	179d	52
14.	Salicyl	$C_{20}H_{28}O_2N_6S$	200d	61
15.	Cinnamyl	$C_{21}H_{30}ON_6S$	217d	60
16.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	$C_{21}H_{32}O_2N_6S$	215d	71
17.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	$C_{20}H_{27}ON_6S$	189d	59
18.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	$C_{20}H_{27}ON_6S$	227d	54
2-Aryl-3-(2',4'-dibutylamino-s-triazin-6'-yl)-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinones				
19.	Phenyl	$C_{21}H_{30}ON_6S$	300	59
20.	Anisyl	$C_{22}H_{32}O_2N_6S$	220d	62
21.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	$C_{21}H_{30}O_2N_6S$	210d	62
22.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	$C_{21}H_{30}O_2N_6S$	300	60
23.	Salicyl	$C_{21}H_{30}O_2N_6S$	300	69
24.	Cinnamyl	$C_{22}H_{32}ON_6S$	300	70
25.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	$C_{22}H_{34}O_2N_6S$	220d	55
26.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	$C_{21}H_{29}ON_6S$	228d	52
27.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	$C_{21}H_{29}ON_6S$	300	73
2-Aryl-3-(2',4'-dibutylamino-s-triazin-6'-yl)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones				
28.	Phenyl	$C_{22}H_{30}O_2N_6S$	> 300	60
29.	Anisyl	$C_{23}H_{32}O_2N_6S$	200d	71
30.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	$C_{22}H_{30}O_2N_6S$	> 300	59
31.	<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	$C_{22}H_{30}O_2N_6S$	> 300	55
32.	Salicyl	$C_{22}H_{30}O_2N_6S$	> 300	58
33.	Cinnamyl	$C_{23}H_{32}O_2N_6S$	> 300	63
34.	3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl	$C_{23}H_{34}O_2N_6S$	> 300	64
35.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	$C_{22}H_{29}ON_6S$	179	60
36.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	$C_{22}H_{29}ON_6S$	> 300	69

*Elemental analyses found satisfactory.

2-Phenyl-3-(2',4'-dibutylamino-s-triazin-6'-yl)-4-thiazolidinone : Thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) was added to 2,4-dibutylamino-6-benzalamino-s-triazine (0.01 mol) in benzene (25 ml) and refluxed for 6 h. The contents were diluted with cold water. The upper organic layer was washed with aqueous

20), 3,4-diethoxyphenyl (17-23) and cinnamyl (18-21). The most active among 2-aryl-3-(2',4'-dibutylamino-*s*-triazin-6'-yl)-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinones are bearing (alongwith the zone of inhibition in mm), R=phenyl (17-23), anisyl (17-24), *p*-hydroxyphenyl (19-22), *m*-hydroxyphenyl (17-22), salicyl (17-22), 3,4-dimethoxyphenyl (18-22), *p*-chlorophenyl (19-20) and *o*-chlorophenyl (17-18). In case of 2-aryl-3-(2',4'-dibutylamino-*s*-triazin-6'-yl)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones, maximum activity was shown by those compounds bearing (alongwith the zone of inhibition in mm), R=anisyl (17-24), *p*-hydroxyphenyl (17-22), *m*-hydroxyphenyl (18-20), salicyl (18-19), cinnamyl (18-21), 3,4-dimethoxyphenyl (17-20).

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Studies on Benzimidazole. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-(α -Arylamino-benzyl)benzimidazoles and 2-(2',3'-Diaryl-4'-keto-5'-thiazolidinyl)methylbenzimidazoles

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BENZIMIDAZOLE derivatives possess anti-malarial¹, local anaesthetic², antipyretic³, anti-bacterial⁴, goitrogenic⁵ and antibiotic⁶ activities.

α -Substituted-arylacetic acids possess analgesics⁷, antilipamic⁸ and antiinflammatory⁹ activities. 4-Thiazolidinones are known for their biological activities, like hypnotic¹⁰, anaesthetic¹¹, antifungal¹², etc. The α -arylaminoacetonitriles¹⁴ obtained by the action of different aromatic amines on different aromatic aldehydecyanohydrin were treated with concentrated sulphuric acid for 24 h leading to the formation of amide. The amides were then refluxed with aqueous sodium hydroxide to give α -arylamino-phenylacetic acid¹⁵. The arylaminophenyl acetic acids were condensed with *o*-phenylenediamine to get benzimidazole of type 1. The aromatic amine

like aniline, *p*-iodoaniline, *p*-aminoacetophenone, and *o*-phenetidine were condensed with aromatic aldehydes like benzaldehyde, and hydroxy-, bromo-, chloro- and methoxy-benzaldehyde to get the Schiff bases which were then condensed with thiomalic acid to obtain 2,3-diaryl-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone^{13,16}. They were condensed with *o*-phenylenediamine to get benzimidazoles of type 2. The constitution was supported by ir spectra (KBr), $\nu_{\max}$ 3 000, 3 200 (NH), 850 and 890 cm^{-1} (polymeric association) through intermolecular hydrogen bond¹⁷. The products were screened for anti-bacterial activity.

TABLE 1—2-(α -ARYLAMINO-BENZYL)BENZIMIDAZOLES (1)

R	R'	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
Phenyl	Phenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₃	158-60	62
Phenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃	151-53	63
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃	184-85	69
Phenyl	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	162	61
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	192-93	68
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ Cl	148-49	61
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Aceto-phenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O	128-30	67
<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenyl	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ ClN ₃	172-73	60
<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenyl	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ ClN ₃	180-81	61

Antibacterial activity: All benzimidazoles were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by cup-plate method¹⁸ using propylene glycol at a concentration 100 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of the test solution. 2 (where ; R=phenyl ; and R'=phenyl, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolyl, *o*- and *p*-anisyl) showed good activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* (30 mm). In case of compounds of type 2 except R'=phenyl, *o*-ethoxyphenyl, *p*-iodophenyl, *p*-acetophenyl and R=phenyl, 3,5-dibromo-3-hydroxyphenyl, are highly active against *S. aureus* (zone of inhibition 38-44 mm).